

QUICK PHOTO GUIDE TO THE SOUTH AFRICAN NEOSCONA SPECIES

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DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., HADDAD, C.R., FOORD, S.H., LOTZ, L.N. & WEBB P. 2022a. *The Araneidae of South Africa. Version 2: part 2 (E-Ne)*. South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 64 pp. <https://doi:10.5281/zenodo.6619195>

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1. *Neoscona alberti* (Strand, 1913)

2. *Neoscona angulatula* (Schenkel, 1937)

3. *Neoscona blondeli* (Simon, 1885)

4. *Neoscona chiarinii* (Pavesi, 1883)

5. *Neoscona hirta* (C. L. Koch, 1844)

6. *Neoscona kivuensis* Grasshoff, 1986

7. *Neoscona moreli* (Vinson, 1863)

8. *Neoscona novella* (Simon, 1907)

9. *Neoscona penicillipes* (Karsch, 1879)

10. *Neoscona quadrigibbosa* Grasshoff, 1986

11. *Neoscona quincasea* Roberts, 1983

12. *Neoscona rapta* (Thorell, 1899)

13. *Neoscona rufipalpis* (Lucas, 1858)

14. *Neoscona subfusca* (C.L. Koch, 1837)

15. *Neoscona theisi theisiella* (Tullgren, 1910)

16. *Neoscona triangula* (Keyserling, 1864)

17. *Neoscona vigilans* (Blackwall, 1865)

